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Call for "Executive Letters"

Dear executive,

Aiming to strengthening the technological knowledge used in the national industry and to bring the research community closer to market and industry agents, the Journal of Contemporary Administration (RAC) is pleased to invite you to write us an "Executive Letter", to be published in a future issue of the journal. The goal of an Executive Letter is to provide the channel by which executives can express their worries and discuss important topics (i.e., empirical problems that your organization might be facing) with the academic community. We believe that your Executive Letter will help fostering applied academic research that might solve the problem(s) you describe in it. We present next a template of an "Executive letter" and a brief description of the Journal of Contemporary Administration.

What you will gain:

- . Your letter will be published in a future edition of the Journal of Contemporary Administration;
- . Your letter will be published in the Journal of Contemporary Administration's official repository and will receive a persistent, citable, and interoperable identifier (i.e., a DOI number)
- . Your content will be accessed by the journal's readers, which includes international researchers, professors of management (and associated fields), Ph.D., masters, and MBA students, and practitioners from several industries;
- . Your letter could foster high-level academic research to address the problem you are describing that is important to your organization or industry;
- . You may work close to agents in the research community to solve the problem of your organization.

Please, feel free to contact us if you need more information.

Best wishes,

Wesley Mendes-da-Silva and Henrique Castro Martins.

Wesley Mendes-da-Silva
(FGV/EAESP)

Henrique Castro Martins
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Template of an "Executive Letter"

Context of your organization

[400 to 1.000 words and a maximum of 10 bullets]

Describe here the context of your organization or industry, the organization size, the market size, etc.

The problem

[400 to 1.000 words and a maximum of 10 bullets]

Describe here the problem that your organization or industry faces. What technological challenges, structural challenges, economic context, etc. that lead to the issues you want to find a solution for.

Research questions that you think are interesting to your organization

[400 to 1.000 words and 5 to 10 bullets]

Describe in bullets the questions you believe are important to your organization's problem and might be interesting to be addressed in academic research. Examples:

- . How to solve the problem X in the industry Y?
- . What are the effects of the changes X in the sector Y?
- . How do individuals from X behave facing changes in Y?
- . Etc.

Additional mandatory information

- . A picture in high definition
- . A short bio [up to 200 words]
- . E-mail address

To submit your Executive Letter, please check the [submission instructions in the journal's website](#).

Should you have any questions, please send an e-mail to the Editors.

ABOUT THE JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ADMINISTRATION (RAC)

The Journal of Contemporary Administration (Revista de Administração Contemporânea – RAC) was established in 1997 and is published bimonthly (continuous publication) by ANPAD (Brazilian Academy of Management), with open-access to its full text (peer-reviewed) content online. Registered under ISSN 1982-7849 (online) and ISSN 1415-6555 (print version from 1997 to 2010). The journal publishes articles on theoretical development and theoretical-empirical work in the area of Administration and Accounting, aligned with Open Science practices: open data, materials and open source, as well as the dissemination of additional information related to the editorial process. This journal is a member of, and subscribes to the principles of, the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE) for scholarly publication. The Journal of Contemporary Administration (RAC) is the leading academic journal in its field, with high quality peer-reviewed contributions. Therefore, we pay special attention to the role of RAC: to be a reliable source of data, information, and knowledge. In addition, RAC, through its editorial scope, prioritizes works that explore themes relevant to society. To do so, it uses the themes highlighted in the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). RAC is a pluralistic and unorthodox business journal in the field of management research, primarily concerned with issues relating to the links between strategy and competitive management, and provides research findings on systems and standards, corporate management tools, organizations and management, specific industry sectors, and answers to contemporary issues such as development, community resilience, inequality, consumption, technology, and climate change.

Read more about it: <https://rac.anpad.org.br>

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